

PRELIMINARY HPTLC FINGERPRINTING AND QUALITATIVE IDENTIFICATION OF RUTIN IN ETHANOLIC LEAF EXTRACT OF *RUTA GRAVEOLENS LINN*

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ABSTRACT

Ruta graveolens Linn. commonly called garden rue, is a medicinal plant known for its rich content of bioactive secondary metabolites, including flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and alkaloids. This study aimed to perform preliminary HPTLC fingerprinting and qualitatively identify rutin in the ethanolic leaf extract of *R. graveolens*. The leaves were collected, authenticated, shade-dried, and extracted using 70% ethanol via Soxhlet extraction. HPTLC analysis was conducted on precoated silica gel 60 F254 plates with a mobile phase composed of ethyl acetate:methanol:water:formic acid (7.5:1.5:0.5:0.1). Visualization was carried out under white light, UV 254 nm, and UV 366 nm, followed by densitometric scanning for peak evaluation. The extract displayed a complex chromatographic profile with multiple peaks, and comparison with standard rutin showed closely matching R_f values, confirming its presence. These findings indicate that HPTLC is a reliable and efficient technique for the qualitative detection of rutin

and other phytoconstituents in *R. graveolens* leaves. The established chromatographic fingerprint can serve as a reference for future standardization, quality control, and further phytochemical studies of this medicinal plant.

KEYWORDS: *Ruta garveolens Linn*, HPTLC, flavonoids, alakloids.

INTRODUCTION

Medicinal plants have long been integral to human culture, serving as a primary source of therapeutic agents across virtually all civilizations. They are considered valuable reservoirs of traditional medicine, and many modern drugs are derived from these plants. For millennia, humans have utilized medicinal plants not only to treat various health conditions but also to enhance food flavor, preserve food, and prevent disease outbreaks. The biological properties of these plants are primarily attributed to the secondary metabolites they produce, which are responsible for their therapeutic effects worldwide.^[1]

Ruta graveolens, commonly known as garden rue, is a strongly scented, small evergreen subshrub or semi-woody perennial belonging to the Rutaceae family. It is widely recognized for its aromatic properties and medicinal applications.^[2] Various secondary metabolites, including alkaloids, coumarins, flavonoids, ketones, terpenoids, and organic acids, have been detected in different parts of the *Ruta graveolens* plant.^[3] Rue grows extensively throughout the Mediterranean and temperate regions of Asia. The whole plant holds medicinal value and has been traditionally used to treat a range of conditions such as kapha and vata imbalances, strangury, fever, flatulence, and epilepsy. Fresh plant material serves as a repellent for scorpions and insects, while the leaves and seeds, when boiled in olive oil, are applied topically to relieve rheumatic pain and reduce swelling.^[4]

HPTLC is a highly versatile and modern analytical technique, valued for its precision, accuracy, and ability to assess uniformity, purity, and assay results. It can efficiently handle multiple samples of diverse compositions, offering a time-saving and cost-effective solution with minimal troubleshooting, providing faster analysis compared to other chromatographic methods.^[5] High-performance thin-layer chromatography (HPTLC) is gaining wider use in pharmaceutical analysis. Improvements in stationary phases and the use of densitometers have enabled HPTLC to achieve precision and accuracy comparable to high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) for certain applications.^[6]

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Collection, authentication and drying of plant material

Leaves of *Ruta graveolens* L. were collected on January 7, 2025, from Mannuthy, Thrissur. The plant was identified and authenticated by Dr. Ranjusha A. P., head of the Botany Department at NSS College, Ottapalam. The collected leaves were shade-dried for 10–14 days and then ground into powder using a mixer grinder.

Preparation of ethanolic extract

25 g of dried, coarsely powdered plant material was placed in a thimble and inserted into a Soxhlet extractor. The extractor was connected to a round-bottom flask containing 500 ml of 70% ethanol and fitted with a reflux condenser. When heated, the ethanol vaporized, condensed, and repeatedly percolated through the plant material, extracting its soluble compounds. This process was carried out for several hours, allowing the extract to collect in the flask. After extraction, the ethanol was removed by evaporation, and the resulting concentrated residue was preserved for later use.

HPTLC analysis

HPTLC analysis was conducted using precoated silica gel 60 F254 plates (0.2 mm thickness; E. Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) as the stationary phase. Samples (1.0 μ L) were applied as bands with a CAMAG Linomat 4 automatic applicator fitted with a 100 μ L Hamilton syringe (Bonaduz, Switzerland). The plates were developed in a CAMAG ADC 2 system within a glass twin-trough chamber (6.0 \times 10.0 cm) pre-saturated with a mobile phase composed of ethyl acetate: methanol: water: formic acid (7.5:1.5:0.5:0.1). Visualization was performed using a CAMAG TLC Visualizer at 254 nm and 366 nm. Plates were derivatized with anisaldehyde–sulphuric acid reagent and documented under visible light. Densitometric scanning was carried out with a CAMAG Scanner 3 at 254 nm and 366 nm, and data were acquired and analyzed using CAMAG win CATS software.

RESULT

HPTLC analysis of ethanolic extract of *Ruta graveolens* linn(EERG)

Graph 1: All tracks at all measured wavelengths.

Graph 2: All Tracks at Wavelength 254nm.

Graph 3: HPTLC chromatogram of ethanolic extract of *Ruta graveolens* at 254 nm.

Table 1: HPTLC Peak Profile of EERG at 254 nm.

Graph 4: HPTLC Chromatogram of Standard Rutin at 254 nm.

Table 2: HPTLC peak profile of standard Rutin at 254 nm.

Graph 5: All tracks at Wavelength 366nm.

Graph 6: HPTLC Chromatogram of EERG at 366 nm.

Table 3: HPTLC peak profile of EERG at 366 nm.

Graph 7: HPTLC chromatogram of standard Rutin at 366 nm.

Table 4: HPTLC Peak Profile of Standard Rutin at 366 nm.

The ethanolic extract of *Ruta graveolens* leaves (EERG) was analyzed using HPTLC and compared with the standard marker compound, rutin. At 254 nm, the extract showed thirteen peaks with Rf values between 0.03 and 0.87, with a major peak at Rf 0.86 (27.10% area) and another significant peak at Rf 0.78 (23.44% area). The standard rutin chromatogram at the same wavelength exhibited five peaks, including a major peak at Rf 0.82 (50.73% area) and additional peaks at Rf 0.31, 0.58, and 0.93. The close correspondence of Rf values between the extract (Rf 0.78–0.86) and standard rutin (Rf 0.82–0.88) indicates the presence of rutin in the extract. At 366 nm, the extract displayed ten peaks, with notable peaks at Rf 0.81 (32.62% area) and Rf 0.32 (21.85% area). Standard rutin at 366 nm showed five peaks, including a major peak at Rf 0.36 (57.38% area) and another at Rf 0.85–0.89 (18.36% area). The overlapping Rf values of the extract (Rf 0.81–0.91) and standard rutin (Rf 0.85–0.89) further confirm rutin's presence under long-wave UV. Comparison of Rf values, retention behavior, and peak areas validates rutin as a phytoconstituent of *Ruta graveolens* leaf extract, alongside several other unidentified compounds.

HPTLC chromatogram visualized under a white light, UV 254nm and UV 366 nm

Fig. 1: photographs of HPTLC chromatogram of EERG.

Under normal white light, the ethanolic extract of *Ruta graveolens* leaves (EERG) exhibited multiple visible bands of varying intensity. The standard rutin appeared as a distinct yellowish band at its characteristic Rf value, while the extract showed similar yellowish bands along with additional faint brownish and greenish spots, indicating the presence of rutin along with other phytoconstituents.

At 254 nm (short-wave UV), the chromatogram displayed dark blue to black quenching bands on a green fluorescent background. The extract showed several prominent quenching bands, notably at Rf 0.78–0.86, which corresponded to the sharp dark band of rutin at Rf \approx 0.82. Additional dark spots at lower Rf values suggested the presence of other phenolic compounds.

At 366 nm (long-wave UV), the extract exhibited multiple fluorescent bands in different colors. A prominent bright greenish-yellow fluorescent band appeared around Rf 0.81–0.91, matching the rutin standard band at Rf 0.85–0.89. Other bands showing blue, violet, and faint green fluorescence indicated the presence of a variety of flavonoids and related compounds in the extract.

CONCLUSION

The preliminary HPTLC analysis of the ethanolic leaf extract of *Ruta graveolens* Linn revealed the presence of diverse phytoconstituents, including flavonoids, phenolic compounds, and other secondary metabolites. Comparison with the standard marker rutin confirmed its presence, as demonstrated by closely aligned Rf values and similar band patterns under white light, UV 254 nm, and UV 366 nm. The extract displayed a complex chromatographic profile with multiple peaks and bands, reflecting its rich chemical composition.

These findings highlight HPTLC as a reliable and efficient method for the qualitative detection of rutin and other bioactive compounds in *Ruta graveolens* leaf extract. The study establishes a preliminary fingerprint that can serve as a basis for future standardization, quality assessment, and further phytochemical research on this medicinal plant.

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REFERENCES

1. Dar RA, Shahnawaz M, Qazi PH. General overview of medicinal plants: A review. The journal of phytopharmacology, 2017; 6(6): 349-51.
2. Malik AA, Mir SR, Ahmad J. Ruta graveolens L. essential oil composition under different nutritional treatments. Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research, 2013; 17(7): 885-90.
3. Aliotta G, Cafiero G. Biological properties of rue (Ruta graveolens L.): Potential use in sustainable agricultural systems. In Principles and Practices in Plant Ecology, 2023 Jul 21; 551-563. CRC Press.
4. Vijendrakumar RC, Sreeramu BS, Shankarappa TH, Santhosh KV, Mallikarjuna Gowda AP, Umesha K. Effect of liquid bio fertilizers on growth, yield and survival of seedlings in garden rue (Ruta graveolens Linn.). Plant Archives, 2014; 14(1): 171-5.
5. Jain A, Parashar AK, Nema RK, Narsinghani T. High performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC): A modern analytical tool for chemical analysis. Current Research in Pharmaceutical Sciences, 2014 Mar 30: 8-14.
6. Shewiyo DH, Kaale EA, Risha PG, Dejaegher B, Smeyers-Verbeke J, Vander Heyden Y. HPTLC methods to assay active ingredients in pharmaceutical formulations: A review of the method development and validation steps. Journal of pharmaceutical and biomedical analysis, 2012 Jul 1; 66: 11-23.